

Spatial Variability and Geo-Statistics Application for Mapping of Soil Properties and Nutrients in Selected States of Southeastern Nigeria

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Abstract: Soil properties and nutrients vary across landscapes due to natural and human-induced factors. Understanding this spatial variability is essential for precision agriculture, land management, and environmental conservation. The study aimed at investigating the spatial variability of some soil properties and nutrients in selected states of Southeastern Nigeria. The research method used was free survey. Four soil profile pits were dug in Abia and Imo State, guided by parent materials (Coastal plain Sand, Imo Clay Shale, Bende-Amaeke Formation and Nsukka Formation). Five soil samples were collected from each profile pit, giving rise to twenty soil samples. Semivariogram techniques were used to investigate the variability among soil properties while OK interpolation method was used to interpolate the un-sampled soil location. The studied soils had friable consistency at the epipedon, which became firm at the underlying horizons. Sand, silt and clay fractions ranged from 24 g/kg to 926 g/kg. Bulk density of the soils increased down the soil profile. Strong to moderate acidic soil condition ranging from 3.52 – 4.26 was identified. Low organic carbon was recorded in the study, ranging from 3.48 to 20.77 g/kg. Moderate base saturation was observed ranging from 32.98 to 70.00%. Three prediction maps were developed using best fitted Geostatistical models (Gaussian, and exponential). The range of spatial dependence is between 5.56 and 42.04 %. These results will be useful for digital soil mapping, site specific management and also provide further knowledge for precision farming.

Keywords: *Geostatistics, Spatial Variability, Parent Materials, Semivariogram, Ordinary Kriging.*

Introduction

The application of spatial variability analysis and geostatistics in soil mapping provides valuable insights for soil fertility and environmental management as well as sustainable agriculture. Soil management systems play an important role in sustainable agriculture and environmental quality. Management practices have greater effect on the direction and degree of changes in soil properties (Kilic et al., 2012).

A soil management system such as tillage, extreme irrigation and improper fertilizer use and application creates unsuitable changes in soil properties. Some researchers such as (Cambardella and Elliott, 1992; Lal et al., 1994; Paz-Gonzalez et al., 2000) have studied the changes in soil properties and its effects to the ecosystem. The most important effect of soil tillage on nutrients is the decrease of cation exchange capacity (CEC) which is attributable to the reduction of soil organic matter (Paz-Gonzalez et al., 2000). Soil tillage systems lead to increase of soil pH, base saturation, and extractable phosphorus (Paz-Gonzalez et al., 2000). Soils are essential to human survival, and they provide a wide diversity of ecosystem services. Effective soil management requires an understanding of soil distribution pattern within the landscape.

Soil properties vary spatially based on parent materials by both intrinsic (soil forming factors) and extrinsic (soil management practices). The physical and chemical properties of soil are influenced by parent materials and soil management system. The variation of soil properties should be monitored and quantified to understand the effects of land use and management system on soils.

Geostatistical method have been used successfully for predicting spatial variability of soil properties (Cambardella et al., 1994; Kilic et al., 2012). Geostatistics application have captured the heterogeneity of soil properties of the area, thereby making geostatistics ideal for more accurate mapping and targeted management. Geostatistics promotes understanding in the variability of soil properties. Advances have been made towards extraordinary digital systems for utilization in soil fertility examination. Pedometrics, through geostatistics is a collection of tools that can be used to analyze and predict spatial or temporal variability of values of spatially correlated data (Obrosiak and Dorozhynskyy, 2017).

Hence, this study was carried out to model spatial variability of soil properties and their mapping in selected states of Southeastern

Nigeria with the objectives (1) to investigate the spatial variability of soil properties and nutrients in selected states of Southeastern Nigeria using Semivariogram and Ordinary Kriging (2) to interpolate the un-sampled location using ordinary kriging interpolation method (3) and to generate attribute maps showing the interpolated results. The results will be useful for enhancement of agriculture production, government policy making and for further research by scientists. The study enhances precision agriculture and supports policymakers in making informed land management decisions.

Materials and methods

Study Area

This study was carried out in two states of Southeastern Nigeria namely; Abia and Imo States. The criteria for the selection were based on their parent materials for spatial continuity, for prediction and development of kriged map, in consideration that they have common boundary. The studied parent materials in Imo state are; Coastal plain sand and Imo clay shale. While the studied parent materials in Abia state are; Bende Amaeke formation and Nsukka formation. Average elevation of the study area is 110 m, the area has tropical wet and dry climate due to the rainy and dry seasons. Rainfall occurs between the month of March and October and four months of dry season between November and February.

Figure 1 Location map of the sampling points at Abia and Imo State Southeastern Nigeria.

Figure 2 Geology map of the study sites in Abia State Southeastern, Nigeria.

Figure 3 Geology map of the study sites in Imo State Southeastern, Nigeria.

Sample Collection

A reconnaissance field study was carried out for the purpose of identifying the parent materials with the help of a geology map through which mapping units were delineated. Four (4) profile pits were dug at four (4) different parent materials in the selected states; Umuagwo in Ohaji/Egbema local government area of Imo state for Coastal plain sand; Umuna in Onuimo local government area of Imo state for Imo clay shale; Uzoakoli in Bende local government area for Bende Amaeke formation in Abia state and Ikeagha in Isiukwuato local government area in Abia state for Nsukka formation as shown in figure 1 to figure 3, and described according to FAO guidelines for soil description (FAO, 2006)

and sampled according to the genetic horizons from bottom layer to the topmost layer using free sampling method. Criteria for delineation include softness, presence of root, colour and presence of macro fauna.

Laboratory Analyses and Data Analyses

The soil samples were air dried and crushed gently in order to reduce the effect of clods. Two (2) millimeter sieves were used to sieve the soil for routine analysis. The soil samples were subjected to various physical and chemical laboratory analyses, which were used to carry out Geo-statistics analysis.

Physical Properties

Particle Size Determination: Particle size distribution was determined using hydrometer method according to Gee and Or (2002), Calgon or sodium hexametaphosphate (NaPO_3)₆ solution was used as dispersant.

Bulk Density: This was determined by the core method as described by Grossman and Reinsch (2002)

Gravimetric Moisture Content: Moisture content was described gravimetrically (Gardner, 1986)

Porosity: Total porosity was calculated from the results of the bulk density (Vomocil, 1965):

Chemical Properties

Soil pH which was measured in 1:2.5 soil/water suspensions (Hendershot et al., 1993).

Soil Organic Carbon and Organic Matter:

Soil organic carbon (SOC) was analyzed by Walkey and Black method as described by Nelson and Sommers (1982). Soil organic matter was derived by multiplying the value of soil organic carbon by Van Bemmelen's correction factor of 1.724.

Total Nitrogen was measured by micro-kjeldahl digestion method (Bremner and Mulvaney, 1982).

Available phosphorus was determined calorimetrically using Bray (11) method (Olsen and Sommers, 1982).

Exchangeable bases (Sodium, Potassium, Calcium and Magnesium). Exchangeable sodium and potassium was extracted using 1N NH₄OAc using flame photometry (Jackson, 1964). While Exchangeable Magnesium and Calcium were evaluated by ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) titration method (Thomas, 1988).

Exchangeable acidity was evaluated titrimetrically (McLean, 1982)

Effective Cation Exchange Capacity was calculated from the summation of all exchangeable bases and exchangeable acidity (IITA, 1982).

Base Saturation was computed. Base Saturation (%) = (Basic cations / CEC) × 100

Geo-statistics Analyses

Geostatistical technique of semivariogram analysis was used to determine the spatial variability of soil properties, and its distribution (Pravat, et al., 2016). Semivariogram was used as the basic tool to examine the spatial distribution structure of the soil properties based on the regionalized variable theory and intrinsic hypotheses (Nielsen and Wendroth, 2004). The ordinary kriging (OK) interpolation method was used for prediction of the values of the unmeasured sites (un-sampled locations).

The GPS readings taken in degrees and minutes were changed to meters and kilometers using Arc view GIS 10.2 version. The western edge of southeastern Nigeria was taken as zero point on X axis, while the southern end of the southeastern map as zero on Y axis.

Graphic lines were drawn at regular intervals on the map. Points were made on the map sheets from where the samples were collected and then x and y readings were noted from the map for further analysis.

Statistical Analyses

Data collected from the study site was subjected to basic statistical analysis. The basic statistics used in this study is Coefficient of Variation (CV) which was used to measure the variability among the studied Soils. The CV was ranked as follows: <15% low variation, 16-35% moderate variation, and >35% high variation (Wilding et al., 1994), while mean was used to get the range of values of the results for better discussion.

Results and Discussion

Physical Properties

The physical properties of soils of Coastal plain sand, Imo clay shale, Bende Amaeke formation and Nsukka formation were presented in Table 1. Sand-sized particles dominated other primary particles in the study sites. The parent material could be the reason for the higher sand values of the area. Sand fraction generally decreased down the profile with mean values as follows: 926 g/kg at Coastal plain sand, 356 g/kg at Imo clay shale, 292 g/kg at Bende Amaeke formation, and 766 g/kg Nsukka formation. Clay contents had irregular distribution, but were observed

to increase with depth. Ignatius et al. (2021) described this as clay migration by lessivage to produce the process of illuviation. Mean clay contents recorded were; 57.2 g/kg at Coastal sand, 242 g/kg at Imo clay shale, 614 g/kg at Bende Amaeke formation, and 210 g/kg Nsukka formation. The least value of clay was recorded in coastal plain sand, while the highest value was found at Bende Amaeke formation; this could be as a result of soil forming processes of the studied soils. Bulk densities of the soils of the study area increased down the profile, this is an implication that there is less organic matter present in the sub-surface horizons. Results of bulk densities were less than the critical limits for root restriction (1.75 – 1.85 g/cm³) (Soil Survey Staff, 2003). Moisture content decreased as depth increased. The percentage porosity was high at the top soil of all the studied pedons which could be as a result of the presence of organic matter. Total porosity of the studied soil declined down the profile due to the clay content which enters into the pores and blocks them, thereby reducing the total porosity (Ignatius, 2021). It was observed that the lower the bulk density, the higher the total porosity.

Table 1 Physical properties of the soil

Parent materials	Horizon	Depth (Cm)	Sand	Silt (g/kg)	Clay	SCR	BD (Mg/m ³)	TP (%)	Θ _m (%)
Coastal plain sand (Imo State)	A	0-21	964	12.8	23.2	0.55	1.08	59.13	14.36
	AB	21-50	964	12.8	43.2	0.3	1.09	58.91	13.98
	Bt ₁	50-80	924	22.8	53.2	0.43	1.10	58.68	10.89
	Bt ₂	80-131	914	42.8	43.2	0.99	1.13	57.43	9.88
	Bt ₃	131-200	864	13	123.2	0.11	1.13	57.40	9.8
	Mean		926	62.42	57.2	0.48	1.10	58.31	11.78
	CV (%)		4.48	4.48	67.26	69.42	2.00	1.43	18.89
Imo Clay Shale (Imo State)	A	0-16	310	460	230	2	1.27	52.1	8.61
	AB	16-31	390	440	170	2.58	1.35	49.1	8.36
	Bt1	31-85	400	350	250	1.4	1.38	47.9	8.76
	Bt2	85-140	350	350	300	1.16	1.48	44.2	10.21
	Bt3	140-200	330	410	260	1.57	1.55	41.5	9.11
	Mean		356	402	242	1.74	1.41	46.94	9.01
	CV (%)		10.81	12.61	19.69	32.14	7.83	8.85	8.03
Bende Amaeke Formation (Abia State)	A	0-8	390	70	540	0.13	1.19	55.1	15.2
	AB	8-24	370	70	560	0.13	1.22	54.0	14.8
	Bt1	24-55	210	110	680	0.16	1.27	52.1	15.8
	Bt2	55-110	160	130	710	0.18	1.37	48.3	16.4
	Bt3	110-200	330	90	580	0.16	1.48	44.2	15.6
	Mean		292	94	614	0.15	1.31	50.72	15.56
	CV (%)		34.79	27.74	12.38	15.87	9.10	8.84	3.90
Nsukka Formation (Abia State)	A	0-9	780	20	200	0.10	1.31	50.57	6.2
	AB	9-33	790	20	190	0.11	1.36	48.68	5.3
	Bt1	33-63	760	20	220	0.09	1.39	47.55	7.8
	Bt2	63-101	630	50	320	0.16	1.45	45.28	9.6
	Bt3	101-200	870	10	120	0.08	1.51	43.02	5.4
	Mean		766	24	210	0.11	1.40	47.02	6.86
	CV (%)		11.33	63.19	34.34	26.79	5.55	6.26	26.67

TC = Textural Class, SCR = Silt Clay Ratio, BD = Bulk Density, TP = Total Porosity, Θ_m = Gravimetric Moisture Content, CV = Coefficient of Variation.

Chemical properties

The chemical properties of the studied soils were presented in Table 2. pH in water had a mean value that ranged from 4.48 to 5.28 which could be as a result of leaching, parent material, clay mineralogy and intensity of microbial activities that is ongoing in the studied soils. According to Landon (1991), pH range of 5.6 to 6.5 provides the most satisfactory plant nutrient levels for most crops. Low pH values recorded in this study could be as a result of the dominance of Al³⁺

and H⁺ ions in the soil exchange complex (Soil Survey Staff, 2003). The soil is rated moderate to acidic soil. In the studied pedons, Organic Carbon contents which gave the Organic matter content decreased with soil as soil depth increases. The surface horizons of the soils had the highest proportion of organic matter because most of the organic residues are deposited and incorporated on the soil surface and this could be explained by their dark colour. Total Nitrogen ranged from 0.47 to 3.22 % (4.7 to 32.2 g/kg). Total N across the studied soils were rated moderate

(Agboola and Corey, 1975). Landon, (1991) reported the range of 0.1 to 0.2 % of total N to be low in soils of the tropics. This could be due to rainfall pattern of the area, soil reaction and temperature. Available Phosphorus content of the studied soils was low, because they fall below the critical levels of 10-16 mg/kg (Adeoye and Agboola, 1985). The low level of available P indicates that Phosphorus may be chemically bound as phosphate of iron and aluminium as a result of the observed acidity of the study area. Total Exchangeable Bases (TEB) ranged from 0.81 to 4.26 Cmol/kg. This could be due to intense leaching (sandy nature), weathering (heavy rainfall), and hence low inherent fertility status with regards to the major nutrients. The mean base saturation percentage ranged from 32.98 to 70.03 % which is less than 90 %. This is an indication that soil amendment is required. According to Altemeyer, (1955) base saturation above 90 % provides Luxury levels of nutrients to crop and soil life.

Semivariogram and Spatial Variability of the Studied Soil Properties.

The semivariogram corresponding to each measured soil variable was constructed based on the best fitted model (Figure 4a through 4f) and spatial attributes (Table 3). The models that best fit the studied soil properties were

Gaussian and Exponential model with a nugget effect that ranged from 0.0018 to 0.2320. The nugget effect is the continuity at close range. The range of the spatial dependence was between 27300.0 and 87577.8 m. The variogram range denotes the distance scale beyond which the fitted parameters will not exhibit any spatial correlation (Awal et al., 2019; Vieira et al., 1988), that is, the highest value of variable semivariance can reach. The upper limit of the fitted semivariogram model is represented by the sill value (Webster and Oliver, 2007). The spatial dependence, which is the nugget to sill ratio played a significant role in spatial variability. According to Cambardella et al. (1994) rating, the values < 25 % indicates strong spatial class; values between 25 % - 75 % indicates moderate spatial class; while values > 75 % indicates weak spatial class. From table 3, the following variables: sand, clay, silt clay ratio, bulk density, moisture content, organic carbon, ECEC, pH, TEA, and Avail. P gave strong spatial class with spatial dependence that is below 25 %, indicating that intrinsic factors such as parent material, climate, topography, and rainfall contributed to the variations (Zheng et al., 2009). While Base saturation gave a moderate spatial class with spatial dependence value of 42.04 % which is attributed to both intrinsic and

extrinsic factors such as parent materials, climate, topography, rainfall pattern, fertilization, management system and other human activities (Wu et al., 2010). The outline of the range is showed as the blue line throughout the semivariogram. A line of best fit, a continues or curve is fitted through the cloud of points. The curves increased gradually with increasing spatial distance before stabilizing (Figure 4a-4f). The sampled points were divided into two data sets, the estimated mean value and the measured mean value from the field, which was used to predict the un-sampled location for the development of the kriged maps (Figure 5a-5c). The spatial distribution maps of the studied soil properties were generated from the Gaussian, and Exponential models, which

gave the studied soil properties best fit (Nielsen and Wendroth, 2004). From Figure 5a sand content was highly dominated at the soils of Umuagwo, (Coastal Plain Sand) with values of 869.8 g/kg and above, which is caused by intrinsic factors especially the parent material. While the least value was recorded in Bende Amaeke formation with values less than 258 g/kg. From figure 5c, the soils of Bende recorded the highest value of Organic Carbon 20.37 to 25.98 g/kg while the soils of Umuagwo, recorded the least value of organic carbon (3.48 to 5.76 g/kg). The implication is that the soils of Bende Amaeke formation is more fertile than the soils of coastal plain sand, soil amendment is therefore recommended to the soils of coastal

Table 2 Chemical properties of the soil

Location	Horizon	Depth (Cm)	pH water	pH KCl	OC (g/kg)	TN (%)	Av.P (Mg/kg)	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	K ⁺	Na ⁺	TEB	H ⁺	Al ³⁺	TEA	ECEC	CEC	Bsat (%)	
								← (Cmo/kg) →											
Coastal plain sand (Imo State)																			
	A	0-21	5.08	4.1	7.2	12.4	5.39	0.5	0.25	0.005	0.022	0.78	0.44	trace	0.44	1.22	2.41	63.93	
	AB	21-50	5.13	4.22	3.4	1.4	2.94	0.7	0.3	0.005	0.021	1.03	0.26	trace	0.26	1.29	2.01	79.84	
	Bt ₁	50-80	5.13	4.03	3.6	1.20	3.64	0.5	0.19	0.003	0.021	0.71	0.4	trace	0.4	1.11	2.25	63.96	
	Bt ₂	80-131	5.22	4.17	1.8	0.30	3.43	0.61	0.23	0.003	0.022	0.87	0.4	trace	0.4	1.27	2.06	68.50	
	Bt ₃	131-200	5.22	4.08	1.4	0.80	2.52	0.5	0.16	0.003	0.018	0.68	0.24	trace	0.24	0.92	1.23	73.91	
	Mean		5.16	4.12	3.48	3.22	3.58	0.56	0.23	0.00	0.02	0.81	0.35		0.35	1.16	1.99	70.03	
	CV (%)		1.20	1.82	65.85	159.90	30.68	16.13	23.95	28.83	7.90	17.34	26.21		26.21	13.10	22.82	9.78	
Imo Clay Shale (Imo State)																			
	A	0-16	5.2	4.2	36.4	1.7	9.31	1.32	1.11	0.5	0.37	3.3	1.1	1.8	2.9	6.2	7.4	53.23	
	AB	16-31	5	4	10	0.4	4.06	0.8	1.06	0.44	0.38	2.68	1.24	1.19	2.43	5.11	6.22	52.45	
	Bt ₁	31-85	5.3	4.2	8.8	0.15	2.34	0.88	1.08	0.38	0.24	2.58	1.01	1.29	2.3	4.88	5.74	52.87	
	Bt ₂	85-140	5.5	4.5	6	0.09	1.16	0.22	1.24	0.29	0.18	1.93	0.77	0.99	1.76	3.69	5.23	52.30	
	Bt _{3g}	140-200	5.4	4.4	5.2	0.03	1.04	0.21	1.36	0.24	0.16	1.97	0.81	1.02	1.83	3.8	5.54	51.84	
	Mean		5.28	4.26	13.28	0.47	3.58	0.69	1.17	0.37	0.27	2.49	0.99	1.26	2.24	4.74	6.03	52.54	
	CV		3.64	4.58	98.44	151.70	95.60	69.00	10.88	28.73	39.03	22.74	20.01	26.00	20.83	21.83	14.07	1.01	
Bende Amaeke Formation (Abia State)																			
	A	0-8	5.2	4.3	41.3	1.9	16.33	2.42	0.98	0.31	0.02	3.73	0.66	0.82	1.48	5.21	6.33	71.59	
	AB	8—24	4.8	3.9	28.1	0.6	8.21	2.6	1.13	0.33	0.02	4.08	0.74	0.97	1.71	5.79	6.76	70.47	
	Bt ₁	24-55	4.5	3.6	20.08	0.28	10.11	2.66	1.2	0.41	0.03	4.3	0.63	1.27	1.9	6.2	7.07	69.35	
	Bt ₂	55-110	4.6	3.6	9.16	0.11	5.82	2.7	1.27	0.45	0.05	4.47	0.62	1.23	1.85	6.32	7.4	70.73	
	Bt ₃	110-200	4.8	3.8	5.22	0.30	3.21	2.82	1.36	0.46	0.09	4.73	0.58	2.59	3.17	7.9	8.15	59.87	
	Mean		4.78	3.84	20.77	0.64	8.74	2.64	1.19	0.39	0.04	4.26	0.65	1.38	2.02	6.28	7.14	68.40	
	CV (%)		5.61	7.50	70.27	112.20	56.91	5.57	12.13	17.53	70.23	8.93	9.26	51.14	32.74	15.95	9.63	7.07	
Nsukka Formation (Abia State)																			
	A	0—9	4.5	3.6	23.56	1.56	5.31	0.82	0.33	0.22	0.09	1.46	1.23	1.81	3.04	4.5	5.2	32.44	
	AB	9—33	4.4	3.4	14.3	0.93	2.7	0.97	0.4	0.28	0.09	1.74	1.33	2.35	3.68	5.42	6.02	32.10	
	Bt ₁	33-63	4.5	3.5	7.17	0.36	1.91	0.99	0.49	0.31	0.11	1.9	1.3	2.78	4.08	5.98	6.32	31.77	
	Bt ₂	63-101	4.6	3.7	5.11	0.09	2.6	1.13	0.52	0.44	0.12	2.21	1.11	3.22	4.33	6.54	7.12	33.79	
	Bt ₃	101-200	4.4	3.4	2.83	0.08	1.21	1.78	0.74	0.46	0.15	3.13	2.46	3.41	5.87	9	10.6	34.78	
	Mean		4.48	3.52	10.59	0.60	2.75	1.14	0.50	0.34	0.11	2.09	1.49	2.71	4.20	6.29	7.05	32.98	
	CV (%)		1.87	3.70	79.53	105.30	56.58	32.98	31.38	30.41	22.23	30.77	37.08	23.98	25.07	26.92	29.77	3.84	

OC = Organic Carbon, TN = Total Nitrogen, Av.P = Avialable Phosphorous, Ca = Calcium, Mg = Magnesium, K = Potassium, Na = Sodium, TEB = Total Exchangeable Base, H = Hydrogen, Al = Aluminium, TEA = Total Exchangeable Acidity, ECEC = Effective Cation Exchange Capacity, CEC = Cation Exchange Capacity, Bsat = Base Saturation, CV = Coefficient of Variation.

plain sand to boost the fertility status of the soils, for effective crop productions.

Table 3 Calculated semivariogram

Variable	Nugget	Sill	Partial sill	Range(m)	Spatial Dependence (%)	Spatial class	Model
Sand	0.0324	0.2752	0.2428	28633.3	11.77	Strong	Gaussian
Clay	0.1632	0.6967	0.5335	76977.8	23.43	Strong	Gaussian
Silt clay ratio	0.2320	1.1412	0.9092	28633.3	20.33	Strong	Gaussian
Bulk density	0.0018	0.0121	0.0103	76600.0	14.48	Strong	Gaussian
Moisture content	0.0119	0.2031	0.1913	32033.3	5.84	Strong	Gaussian
pH	0.0018	0.0326	0.0308	27300.0	5.56	Strong	Exponential
Organic carbon	0.0333	0.3869	0.3536	31377.8	8.59	Strong	Gaussian
ECEC	0.0856	0.5346	0.4490	73655.5	16.02	Strong	Gaussian
BS	0.0610	0.1450	0.0841	31600.0	42.04	Moderate	Gaussian
TEA	0.0785	1.1222	1.0437	60577.8	7.00	Strong	Gaussian
Avial. P	0.0874	0.5099	0.4225	40155.6	17.14	Strong	Gaussian

ECEC = Effective Cation Exchange Capacity; BS = Base Saturation; TEA = Total Exchangeable Acidity; Avail. P = Available Phosphorus.

Figure 4a Semivariogram and the best fitting model for Sand Content

Figure 4b Semivariogram and best fitting model for Silt Clay

Figure 4c Semivariogram and best fitting model for pH in 1N KCl

Figure 4d Semivariogram and best fitting model for pH in Water

Figure 4e Semivariogram and best fitting model for Soil Organic Carbon

Figure 4f Semivariogram and best fitting model for Base Saturation

Figure 5a Kriged Map for Sand Content

Figure 5b Kriged Map for Silt Clay Ratio

Figure 5c Kriged Map for Organic Carbon

Conclusion

Soil properties vary with respect to soil intrinsic and extrinsic factors such as parent material, climate, rainfall pattern, topography, fertilization, cropping system, management practices and other human activities. The methodology applied in this study has characterized and acquired quantitative information for investigating and monitoring the variability of the soil properties. The spatial distribution of the studied soil properties gave rise to strong and moderate autocorrelation. Maps of various soil properties showed variation in different parts

and can be managed accordingly. The generated kriged map could be used as a reference for investigating variability of soil properties and nutrients in different parent material for precision farming, and sustainable agricultural production. Hence, a sustainable soil management practices is recommended. Our results will be useful for digital soil mapping and site specification, also serve as a reference point for policy formation in precision farming.

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